

Revision of the General Relativity Guided by Enthalpy Conservation

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Abstract

In spite of its astounding predictability and precision in explaining phenomena to which the exterior Schwarzschild metric is applicable, as far as those related to the FLRW metric and the interior Schwarzschild metric are concerned, Einstein's theory of general relativity has left with us more controversies than legacies. In this paper, I will firstly provide a revision of Einstein's field equation guided by a newly proposed principle of enthalpy conservation, and then present a much simpler alternative theory that is perfectly compatible with Maxwellian electromagnetism.

In the light of the fact that all verifications of the general relativity have been restricted to those related to the exterior Schwarzschild solution in which $T_{\mu\nu}$ can be approximated as zero, the validity of the right-hand side of Einstein's equation actually remains untested to date.

When we adopt energy conservation as the supreme axiom, quantum fluctuation alone cannot explain why such a massive universe can exist for billions of years. The positive energy in our universe shall rather be a mirror image balancing with the negative pressure of vacuum space multiplied by volume, such that the enthalpy of our universe conserves at zero, ever since its birth from nothing.

$$H = U + PV = 0$$

Guided by this alternative principle, and set $P = -\rho c^2$, then the continuity equation for enthalpy is

$$D_\nu \left(T^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{4} g^{\mu\nu} T \right) = 0$$

and the field equation ($\Lambda = 0$) shall be revised to

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} T \right)$$

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(T_{\mu\nu} - \frac{3}{4} g_{\mu\nu} T \right)$$

The Friedmann equations ($K = 0$) for an expanding universe are now

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{4\pi G}{3c^2} (5\rho c^2 - 3P)$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3c^2} (\rho c^2 + 9P)$$

$$5\dot{\rho}c^2 - 3\dot{P} = -12\frac{\dot{a}}{a}(\rho c^2 + P)$$

By a mechanism I will address in a separate paper, energy density of our universe shall be inversely proportional to the square of scale factor, such that the cosmological event horizon constantly expands at the velocity of light.

$$\rho \propto a^{-2} \quad \rightarrow \quad \dot{\rho} = -2\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\rho \quad \rightarrow \quad P = -\frac{1}{9}\rho c^2$$

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = H^2 = \frac{64\pi G\rho}{9}$$

By the same mechanism, the total energy in our universe is rightly 8 times that of visible matter. The extra 7 units are energy of gravitational field, which is indeed the so-called dark matter. In the separate paper, I will discuss the source of discrepancy between my theoretical prediction and the latest data collected by the PLANCK satellite.

Having accepted these assumptions, we may realize that the revised Hubble's constant indicates that 37.6% (8 times of 4.7%) of the critical density ρ_c back-calculated from Einstein's equation can rightly yield 100% of the actual expanding velocity of our universe. The seemingly accelerating expansion of our universe is due to a time-dependent decrease (inversely proportional to the cubic root of the age of our universe) of the mass of all elementary particles, whose detailed mechanism will be addressed in the separate paper as well.

Note that the Friedmann equation for the acceleration of scale factor indicates that the $9P$ in the bracket generally contributes to gravitational acceleration (instead of $3P$ in Einstein's version), it explains the apsidal precession in a much simpler fashion. Let v be the velocity of Mercury's revolution, when v/c is large enough, $T_{\mu\nu}$ of the Sun can no longer be approximated as $diag(\rho c^2, 0, 0, 0)$. Instead,

$$P = \rho \overline{v_x^2} = \rho \overline{v_y^2} = \rho \overline{v_z^2} = \frac{1}{3} \rho v^2$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3c^2}(\rho c^2 + 9P) = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}\rho \left(1 + 3\frac{v^2}{c^2}\right)$$

which perfectly gives the effective centripetal force in Schwarzschild solution.

As for why $9P$ contributes to gravity, in the context of enthalpy conservation, the pressure of matter ($P_m = P$) and the pressure of space (P_s) shall evolve satisfying that the integral of $P_s dV$ through space expansion gives rise to $P_m V$ of the matter in it.

$$P_m r^3 = \iiint_0^r P_s d^3r \rightarrow P_m = \frac{1}{6} P_s$$

$$9P_m V = \frac{3}{2} P_s V = K$$

K is the kinetic energy confined in the space of volume V , suppose the assembly of matter can be macroscopically approximated as a monoatomic gas. Thus, the bracket calculates nothing but the sum of rest energy and kinetic energy, both of them act as sources of gravity.

Having said all that, any successful revision of general relativity within the original paradigm cannot change its embarrassing incompatibility with quantum mechanics. And here comes the final solution to the stagnation.

In short, the Riemannian geometry in general relativity is nothing but calculating the sum of three independent gravitational accelerations:

1) Dynamics of space, which can be either contraction or expansion, depending on the spatial distribution of mass.

2) Universal repulsion between Fermions (on top of space dynamics);

3) Contribution from the existence of pressure (attraction when $P > 0$, repulsion when $P < 0$).

The following Maxwellian equations describe a couple of mutual inductive fields \vec{L} and \vec{Y} , which naturally predict the existence of gravitational waves, assuring that gravity does not violate the locality principle.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{L} = 4\pi G \rho$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{Y} = 0$$

$$\nabla \times \vec{L} = -9 \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{Y}}{\partial t}$$

$$\nabla \times \vec{Y} = \frac{1}{9} \left(4\pi G \vec{m} + \frac{\partial \vec{L}}{\partial t} \right)$$

(\vec{m} for 3-momentum density vector.)

Define 4-mass density vector ρ^μ (γ for Lorentz factor), vector potential \vec{G} , scalar potential ϕ , and 4-gravitational potential G^μ .

$$\rho^\mu = \gamma \left(\rho, \frac{\vec{m}}{c} \right) \quad G^\mu = \left(\phi, 9 \frac{\vec{G}}{c} \right)$$

$$\vec{Y} = \nabla \times \vec{G} \quad \vec{L} = -\nabla \phi - 9 \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{G}}{\partial t}$$

Further define field strength tensors $L^{\mu\nu}$ and $\tilde{L}^{\mu\nu}$ in the same manner to Maxwell's tensors $F^{\mu\nu}$ and $\tilde{F}^{\mu\nu}$,

$$L^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu G^\nu - \partial^\nu G^\mu \quad \tilde{L}^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} L_{\rho\sigma}$$

$$L^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & L_1 & L_2 & L_3 \\ -L_1 & 0 & 9Y_3/c & -9Y_2/c \\ -L_2 & -9Y_3/c & 0 & 9Y_1/c \\ -L_3 & 9Y_2/c & -9Y_1/c & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

then the four equations can be sophisticated as two Lorentz covariant tensor equations.

$$\partial_\nu L^{\mu\nu} = 4\pi G \rho^\mu$$

$$\partial_\nu \tilde{L}^{\mu\nu} = 0$$

To construct the equation of motion, define a 4-vector L^μ composed of \vec{L} , and a correspondent scalar calculating the norm of L^μ .

$$L^\mu = \left(c \frac{d^2 t}{d\tau^2}, \gamma^2 \vec{L} \right) \quad L = \sqrt{L^\mu L_\mu}$$

Then define a mixed tensor whose diagonal components take value of either 1 or -1, depending on whether L as a function is increasing or decreasing with regards to the coordinate in question,

$$\sigma_\nu^\mu = \frac{\partial_\nu L}{|\partial_\mu L|}$$

and a correspondent scalar by contracting indices.

$$\sigma = \sigma_\mu^\mu = \begin{cases} 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 = -2 \text{ (Schwarzschild)} \\ 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 = 4 \text{ (Friedmann \cdot Lemaitre)} \end{cases}$$

Eventually, the equation of motion can be written as

$$\frac{du^\mu}{d\tau} = \frac{L^{\mu\nu} u_\nu}{c} + \sigma L^\mu$$

where u^μ is the 4-velocity vector. The contribution from $\vec{u} \times 9\vec{Y}$ and the magnetic component of the Lorentz force share a perfect analogy. Rotation in the field of mass (\vec{L}) creates a vertical field of momentum (\vec{Y}) whose strength is proportional to the rotating velocity, and according to the Fleming's left-hand rule, particles running in it would feel a centripetal force whose strength is now proportional to the square of velocity.

The scalar σ inverts the direction of space dynamics (\vec{L}) when necessary (depending on the distribution of mass). And as we will see shortly, the Newtonian induction of the Friedmann model is neither a temporary expedient nor a childish trick, but rather wisely pointing out the inherently two-way nature of gravity in a couldn't-be-simpler manner.

Let $P = 0$ as the Newtonian limit, and focus on the 00 component of the revised field equations.

$$R_{00} - \frac{1}{2} g_{00} R = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(\rho c^2 + \frac{1}{4} \rho c^2 \right)$$

$$R_{00} = \frac{16\pi G}{c^4} \left(\rho c^2 - \frac{3}{4} \rho c^2 \right)$$

$$\rightarrow R_{00} = \frac{4\pi G}{c^2} \rho \quad -\frac{1}{2} g_{00} R = \frac{16\pi G}{c^2} \rho$$

This calculation coincides with the Newtonian induction shown in below, supposing that space dynamics is twice sensitive as Fermion repulsion (equivalent to the fact that $\sigma = -2$ in Schwarzschild metric) in terms of the reactivity to the existence of mass.

Fermion repulsion

$$\frac{d^2 r_m}{dt^2} = G \frac{4\pi r_m^3 \rho}{3} \frac{1}{r_m^2} = \frac{4\pi G \rho}{3} r_m \quad (\rho = \text{const.})$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dr_m}{dt} \right)^2 = \frac{2\pi G \rho}{3} r_m^2 \quad \rightarrow \quad \left(\frac{r_m}{r_m} \right)^2 = \frac{4\pi G \rho}{3}$$

Space dynamics

$$\frac{d^2 r_s}{dt^2} = -2G \frac{4\pi r_s^3 \rho}{3} \frac{1}{r_s^2} = -\frac{8\pi G r_0^3 \rho_0}{3} \frac{1}{r_s^2} \quad (\rho = \rho_0 \frac{r_0^3}{r_s^3})$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dr_s}{dt} \right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G r_0^3 \rho_0}{3} \frac{1}{r_s} \quad \rightarrow \quad \left(\frac{r_s}{r_s} \right)^2 = \frac{16\pi G \rho}{3}$$

It persuasively suggests that the first and second term of Einstein's tensor are actually calculating the contributions from Fermion repulsion and space dynamics respectively. $G_{\mu\nu}$ is now endowed with a concrete physical meaning, beyond a conclusion of pure mathematical induction from Bianchi's identity such that $D_\nu G^{\mu\nu} = 0$.